

PMR Spectroscopic Studies on Acetoacet. diethylamide and its Beryllium Chelate*

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Enol-content of acetoacet. diethylamide has been determined by PMR spectroscopic method. Beryllium chelate of acetoacet. diethylamide was prepared and its PMR spectrum recorded for comparison with that of the ligand. Supporting evidences for Meyer's conclusions regarding keto-enols have been obtained from a study of the solvent effect.

THE advantage of proton magnetic resonance technique in studying tautomeric phenomena and hydrogen bonding has been amply demonstrated in recent years¹⁻¹². Possibilities of chemical perturbation, as in the bromine-titration technique of Kurt Meyer¹³ are eliminated in this method. Although so is the case with ultraviolet, Raman and infrared spectroscopic methods, in the use of these latter methods accurate determination of extinction coefficients and proper investigation to ensure that Beer's Law holds good, are necessary if absolute equilibrium constants are required. PMR technique gives directly the absolute value of the equilibrium constant, since intensities of the signals are related to the number of protons involved by a common factor.

its enolate ion in the metal chelate) was used for comparison.

The lowest field signal of acetoacet. diethylamide (at 904 cps., in carbon tetrachloride, Fig. 1) is evidently due to the chelated hydrogen of the enol form. Appearance of this signal at such a low field (the signal occurs at the same field as with acetylacetone⁵) is indicative of strong hydrogen bonding. The marked effect of hydrogen bonding on the resonance frequencies of protons was established very early in the development of nuclear magnetic resonance^{14,15}.

The methynyl proton of the enol form absorbs at 301 cps. The protons of the CH₂ group (between

Fig. I PMR SPECTRUM IN CCl₄

PMR technique has been used in the present investigation for evaluating enol-content of acetoacet. diethylamide. The simpler spectrum of its beryllium chelate (simpler because the ligand exists solely as

the two carbonyl groups of the keto form) absorb at 203 cps. along with the N-ethyl methylenes, which appears as a quartet centred at 200 cps. The methyl hydrogens of the N-ethyl groups show two triplets centred at 65 cps and 68 cps. However, the "65 cps. methyl triplet" appears to be ringing on the

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"68 cps. triplet", the keto and enol signals but being well resolved.

The methyl hydrogens of the keto form (H^k in figure) show singlet at 131 cps., while those of the enol form (H^e) show another singlet at higher field¹⁻³, at 113 cps; almost at the same field as in the beryllium chelate (114 cps. Fig. II). The keto and enol methyl hydrogen signals are separated by 18 cps. This appreciable separation enabled proper comparison of intensities by integration. From the integrated intensities, the enol-content has been calculated as 56.10% (CCl_4).

Fig. II PMR SPECTRUM IN CCl_4

Meyer¹⁶ studied the enol-content of keto enols in equilibrium in solution. Theoretically, the more polar solvents should favour the more polar tautomer, because in this way solvation energy can be maximized. Meyer found that the more polar solvents favoured the keto form of β -diketones and β -keto esters. It is, therefore, to be concluded that Meyer's enols were less polar than the keto forms. As far as is known, such enols are more volatile than the keto forms¹⁷. Both effects support an internally hydrogen bonded structure for enols, whereby considerable decrease in polarity can occur. Wasserman¹⁸ has shown that keto-enols, for which the enolic forms cannot easily undergo intramolecular hydrogen bonding, may exhibit that reverse solvent effect.

In order to examine the dependence of keto-enol ratio on solvent polarity, PMR spectra were recorded also of the acetoacet. diethylamide liquid and of it in deuterioacetone (CD_3COCD_3). In both, the enol-content was found to be considerably less.

	Enol-content
Acetoacet. diethylamide (liquid)	40.00%
Acetoacet. diethylamide (in deuterio-acetone)	24.50%

Experimental

The beryllium chelate of acetoacet. diethylamide was prepared as follows: Basic beryllium carbonate,

$BeCO_3 \cdot Be(OH)_2$, (1.12 g.; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum quantity of hot dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. Acetoacet. diethylamide (6.3 g.; 0.04 mole) was dissolved in water (45 ml.) by adding ammonium hydroxide drop by drop. The latter solution was then added to the former solution slowly with vigorous stirring. Colourless crystals were formed immediately. Filtered, washed with water, sucked dry and recrystallized from benzene-petroleum ether. Yield: 5.5 g. (86%); m.p. 109.5°. Found: C, 60.01; H, 8.93; N, 8.65; Be, 2.79%. $C_{16}H_{28}N_2O_4Be$ requires: C, 59.81; H, 8.72; N, 8.72; Be, 2.80%.

Solutions (1.15 m.) of acetoacet. diethylamide containing a small amount of tetramethylsilane as internal standard were allowed to equilibrate for a week¹⁰, before the spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 NMR spectrometer at 60 Mc; calibration of the chart was done using TMS in deuterated chloroform (436 cps.) Ratio of intensities of H^e and H^k signals, calculated graphically, agreed well with the integrated intensity.

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